

CORRELATION BETWEEN CREATIVITY AND ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

Dr. S. Kalaivani* & V. Suguna**

* Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Annamalai University,
Chidambaram, Tamilnadu

** M.Ed Scholar, Department of Education, Annamalai University,
Chidambaram, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. S. Kalaivani & V. Suguna, "Correlation between Creativity and Achievement of Higher Secondary Students", International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 630-631, 2018.

Copy Right: © IJCRME, 2018 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

The present study aims to know the relationship between creativity of the higher secondary students with achievement. Simple random sampling technique has been used in the selection of the various schools in Cuddalore District. To measure creativity, Creativity Inventory developed by D. Venkataraman – 1998 was used and for achievement score student final exam mark was consider. Result shows that there is a positive and significant correlation between creativity and achievement.

Introduction:

Creativity is the ability to transcend traditional ideas, rules, patterns, relationships, or the like, and to create meaningful new ideas, forms, methods, interpretations, etc.; originality, progressiveness, or imagination: the need for creativity in modern industry. Extensive reading stimulated his creativity. Researchers have seen this as an important because technology is advancing our society and creative problem solving will be needed to cope with these challenges as they arise. In addition to helping with problem solving, creativity also helps students identify problems where others have failed to do so.

Promoting intrinsic motivation and problem solving are two areas where educators can foster creativity in students. Students are more creative when they see a task as intrinsically motivating, valued for its own sake. To promote creative thinking educators need to identify what motivates their students and structure teaching around it. Providing students with a choice of activities to complete allows them to become more intrinsically motivated and therefore creative in completing the tasks.

Teaching students to solve problems that do not have well defined answers is another way to foster their creativity. This is accomplished by allowing students to explore problems and redefine them, possibly drawing on knowledge that at first may seem unrelated to the problem in order to solve it.

Need for the Present Study:

The new National Policy on Education (NPE revised 1998) as well as the new National Senior Secondary School Science (Physics, Chemistry and Biology) curriculum had been sufficiently adjusted to accommodate new trends in science teaching worldwide both in its principles and practices. Poor performance of students in science subjects at the senior secondary school certificate examination (SSCE) can be attributed to inadequate acquisition in competence in chemistry laboratory and also the ability and competence of the male students to the female students in solving problem task in Mathematics related courses and non-attainment of formal operational stage-the age at which students can think in abstraction and logically too. This study therefore focuses on creativity of the higher secondary students.

Objective:

To find out if there is any significant relationship between creativity and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Hypothesis: Based on the objective the hypothesis is formulated

There is no significant relationship between creativity and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Methodology of the Study:

- Method of Study: Normative survey method has been used in the present study.
- Tool: In the present study, the following tool was used to measure the creativity of the higher secondary students. Creativity Inventory developed by D. Venkataraman - 1998
- Sample: The present study includes a sample of 300 higher secondary students of different schools in Cuddalore District based on random sampling technique.

Description of the Tool:

The Creativity Inventory consists of 60 statements which have four options of responses viz., "To a very great extent", "To a great extent", "To some extent", and "No" which has the score of 3, 2, 1 and 0.

The maximum score that an individual can get in this scale is 180 and the minimum is 0.

Correlation Analysis for Creativity and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary Students:

Null Hypothesis:

There is no significant relationship between creativity and academic achievement of higher secondary students. Showing the relationship between creativity and academic achievement scores of higher secondary students

Variables	N	'r' value	Level of Significance
Creativity & Academic Achievement	300	.326**	Significant

It is evident from the table the calculated 'r' value is found to be 0.326 which is significant at 0.01 level. So that the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is inferred that there is significant relationship between creativity and academic achievement of higher secondary students.

Recommendations:

To improve the creativity of the higher secondary students, the following recommendations are made based on the result of the study.

- Establishing purpose and intention of learning.
- Building basic skills of higher secondary students.
- Encouraging acquisitions of domain-specific knowledge among the higher secondary students.
- Stimulating and rewarding curiosity and exploration in learning activities.
- Building motivation, especially internal motivation in academic achievement.
- Encouraging confidence and a willingness to take initiative.
- Focusing on mastery and self-competition among the higher secondary students.
- Promoting supportable beliefs about creativity
- Providing opportunities for choice and discovery in learning activities.

Conclusion:

Thus the analysis of the data generated by the administration of the Creativity inventory to a sample of 300 higher secondary students in Cuddalore District, Tamilnadu has yielded many interesting results, which are summarized in this paper. It is found in the present investigation, that the higher secondary students are having high level of creativity. It is also found that there is a positive and significant relationship between the creativity and academic achievement in of the higher secondary students.

References:

1. Good, Carter .V (1972). Essentials of Educational Research, New York: Appleton-Century Crofts.
2. Khan. J. A. Research Methodology, APH Publishing Corporation, New Delhi.
3. Mumford, M. D. (2003). Where have we been, where are we going? Taking stock in creativity research. Creativity Research Journal, 15, 107–120.
4. Travers, Robert M.W. (1978). An Introduction to Educational Research, New York: McGraw-Hill Book Company.
5. Whitney F.L. (1956). The Elements of Research, Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice-Hall, Inc.
6. Bipin Asthana & Agarwal R.N.(1982). Measurement and Evaluation in psychology and education, Agra.
7. Buch M.B. (1983-88) Fourth Survey of Research in Education, Vol.1. N.C.E.R.T., New Delhi.